

A Survey on Comparative Study of Customer Behaviour in Online and Offline Purchase of Electronic Items in Ahmedabad

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ABSTRACT

Online shopping is quite a new thing these days, although some people are still unaware of it. Although everyone uses the word "shopping" regularly, Internet shopping is becoming more and more popular these days. When everyone goes to shopping, some people get what they need, while others buy more. It means that it can satisfy an internal objective. If someone wants to talk to a close friend or relative, they can send them messages without any charges, search anything on Google, locate someone, express their love towards them through gifts, etc. This is an advantage of modern technology. This study examines consumers who purchase electronic goods online or offline. Even though traditional markets are shrinking due to the expansion of the Internet, some customers still prefer to shop offline. Since it is difficult to buy electronic products online, most people decide to buy offline, while some people prefer to buy online. The overall study aims to determine the percentage of consumers who prefer to purchase electronic items through both offline and online mediums. The research analyses what customers' preferences, decision-making processes and behavior vary between online and offline shopping scenarios. Through the analysis of the relationship between traditional offline merchants and online shopping, this study seeks to identify consumer decision-making variables in the complex market of Ahmedabad

INTRODUCTION

In today's era, the choice of consumer for purchasing electronic items between online and offline has become a critical factor. Now, consumers have unique and immediate access to a wide range of products on e-commerce platforms. As a result of fundamental changes in consumer behaviour, companies in the retail industry are being forced to adapt to this unique landscape. Ahmedabad is a vibrant city in the heart of Gujarat and that is an example of this innovative movement.

Ahmedabad city is a fast-growing economic hub that serves a wide customer base with diverse preferences, population density, and spending habits. Companies need to understand all aspects of consumer behaviour regarding the purchasing of electronic goods so that they can adapt their strategies appropriately. This case study analyses the comparison of consumer behaviour in purchasing electrical items both offline and online in the Ahmedabad market. Companies can gain valuable knowledge to develop targeted marketing strategies and simplify their operational processes by carefully studying the elements that influence these decisions.

There have been many changes in the traditional market with online shopping. This feature offers a wide range of product options, comfort, category evaluation, and a very simple way to find anything in one place. When a consumer purchases goods or services through a digital platform, he or she participates in online shopping. This involves searching the internet to find the seller's website, selecting what you want, and arranging delivery options for you. When there are two sides to every story, some customers remain concerned about security and trust when shopping online, even though it can be extremely useful. They are restricted from online shopping because they follow the concept of touch and feel. Before making a decision, they would like to handle the product and discuss their views about it with friends and relatives. Offline shopping is the process of visiting a store and purchasing your desired brand and item. It could be a large department store or a store associated with small businesses.

For a long time, the product has been purchased from the traditional market. Many customers shop offline as they simply verify the item and take ownership of the item after payment is confirmed. However offline experience can reduce cultural differences in consumers' product perception and can also successfully avoid differences in individual expectations.

Research Objective:

The objective of this research is to thoroughly research, compare, and explain the preferences, decisions, and behaviour of customers while purchasing electronic items through online and offline channels. In the current changing market environment, it is essential to understand customer behaviour in terms of purchasing electrical goods across online and offline channels. The objective is to identify the root causes, catalysts used, and influencing factors that motivate customers to choose one of the two different purchasing modes.

The main objective of this research is to provide a comprehensive understanding of how consumers choose electronic products among these different channels, which will be useful in enhancing marketing strategies and

customer-centric business models. It aims to examine the differences and similarities in consumer behavior through the use of qualitative as well as quantitative strategies. This will provide an understanding of several issues such as the impact of customer service on product variety, pricing, ease of use, trust, and purchasing attitudes. This study seeks to explore the specific behaviour, preferences, and experiences of consumers in both online and offline situations.

LITERATURE REVIEW

For a long time, the structure of five working days per week and the reduction of statutory working hours has been an ongoing issue. As a result, more and more individuals are showing interest in enhancing their quality of life, participating in various social activities, and improving their overall condition. More and more customers in the electronic market want to simply purchase goods from online retailers at whatever time and place they choose. According to Hoffman and Novak (1996), online shopping malls consist of technological systems that allow consumers to purchase goods online instead of offline at stores or shops. (Choi, C., & Bum, C., 2020).

The literature review includes analysis, information, evaluation, and summary of earlier research in the area of offline and online customer behaviour in retailing. It provides readers with a fundamental overview of the variables that influence consumers' decision-making processes when making purchases both offline and online. It also identifies research gaps and gives direction to the study. Understanding the basic ideas of how and why customers behave in particular ways when making purchases, both online and offline, is known as consumer behaviour. Marketers interested in both offline and online retailing will want to learn about consumer purchasing behaviour, which requires understanding the different elements that influence both offline and online consumer behaviour. (SASINDRAN.ND, 2022)

The retail sector is receiving attention from the internet these days, while millions of people shop online, many customers also buy products offline. As a result, after making the payment and checking out the product, customers become loyal to the brand. In the modern world, it is based on the brand's ability to provide high-quality products at affordable prices. This is a common thought that comes to mind when looking at Internet users when they are online: the consumer must choose the channel that best suits his needs and meets his demands in this competitive world. (S. Shalini, N. P. ,2019)

Executive (2021) One can evaluate whether creating retail space is still worthwhile given the increase in online shopping. The number of buyers using mobile devices is increasing over time. Even though online shopping is becoming more and more popular, shopping in stores is still unsustainable. A large number of customers shop offline as well as online. Offline shopping is not online, as the term suggests. The customer comes inside the shop and makes a purchase. Although shopping via the Internet is still common, some consumers still favor buying things in stores. (Himanshi Prajapati, 2022)

The majority of consumers buy goods from stores, department stores, supermarkets, grocery stores, and malls because they are necessities. Ninety percent of people living in industrialized countries no longer farm, so they have

to buy their food and drinks from stores. In addition, they purchase an infinite number of goods to maintain or furnish their homes, overcome problems, or work around them. However, there are other reasons why people go out shopping to ensure their survival. Individuals buy goods that help them stand out from the neighborhood. Going shopping and completing the purchase is full of happiness which mentally boosts the enthusiasm of the person and gives some relief from everyday tasks. (Dr. N. Priyadharshini, 2023)

Research Gap:

There is insufficient significant research related to the studies that specifically focus on the Ahmedabad region of India, even though several studies have examined the variation in consumer behavior between online and offline purchases of various items, including electronic gadgets. There is an inadequate level of data collection that fully examines the complex social and cultural factors influencing consumer behavior, local market trends, and technology infrastructure in this particular geographic region. Gaining an understanding of the unique tastes, convenience factors, trust factors and decision-making processes of Ahmedabad customers can help set up more targeted marketing campaigns and optimized business methods. Creating this knowledge gap through research will help Ahmedabad-based companies improve customer delight and customer satisfaction in the electronic goods retail sector. It is essential to understand how consumers move between different channels, what factors influence their choices, and if the online and offline experiences enhance or conflict with each other to create a joint advertising approach that addresses both channels.

Hypothesis Testing:

H1: There is a significant association between the age of respondents and How Often they shop for electric items such as smartphones, laptops, or gadgets.

H2: There is a significant association between the age of respondents and where they make most of their purchases.

H3: There is a significant association between the age of respondents and customers' preference for online shopping of electronic items.

H4: There is a significant association between the age of respondents and factors influencing customers' choices between online and offline shopping.

H5: There is a significant association between the age of respondents and the comparison of Electronic Products online before making a purchase.

METHODOLOGY

Type of Research	Primary research
Research Design	Descriptive research design
Participants	People living in Ahmedabad city
Area of Research	Ahmedabad
No. of Respondents	66
Sampling Method	Non – probability- Convenient sampling
Data Collection Method	Questionnaire – Google form
Analysis Collected Data	MS Excel

RESULT

Data Analysis

Demographic Summary

The data presents information on the demographic distribution of a sample group based on age, gender, and Educational Background.

Age:

- 1.5% of the participants fall in the 10-18 age range.
- 83.3% fall in the 19-26 age range.
- 13.6% fall in the 27-34 age range.
- 1.5% fall in 34 and above age range.
- The total sample size is 66 participants.

Gender:

- 51.5% of the participants are male.
- 48.5% are female.
- The total sample size is 66 participants.

Educational Background:

- 7.6% of the participants are from High School.
- 33.3% are from Bachelor’s Degree.
- 59.1% are from Master’s Degree.
- The total sample size is 66 participants.

Cronbach’s Alpha

Table 1. Reliability Statistics

Cronbach's Alpha	N of Items
.714	15

*Source: SPSS software

As the alpha value is more than 0.07 i.e. 0.714 the data is reliable

Hypothesis testing

Chi-Square Analysis

H1: There is a significant association between the age of respondents and How Often they shop for electric items such as smartphones, laptops, or gadgets.

Table 2: Crosstab: Age & How Often Do You Shop for Electric Items Such as Smartphones, Laptops, or Gadgets?

		How often do you shop for electric items such as smartphones, laptops, or gadgets?				Total
		Frequently	Occasionally	Rarely	Never	
Age	10-18	0	0	1	0	1
	19-26	6	22	23	4	55
	27-34	1	1	6	1	9
	34 and Above	0	0	0	1	1
Total		7	23	30	6	66

Source: SPSS software

Table 3. Chi-Square Tests

	Value	df	Asymp. Sig. (2-sided)
Pearson Chi-Square	14.372^a	9	.110
Likelihood Ratio	9.960	9	.354
Linear-by-Linear Association	2.706	1	.100
N of Valid Cases	66		

Source: SPSS software

a. 12 cells (75.0%) have an expected count of less than 5. The minimum expected count is .09.

Interpretation: As the p value is more than 0.05, hence we reject H1. This shows that there is no significant association between the age of respondents and How Often they shop for electric items such as smartphones, laptops, or gadgets.

H2: There is a significant association between the age of respondents and where they make most of their purchases.

Table 3: Crosstab: Age & Where Do Customers Make Most of Their Purchases?

		When shopping for electronic items, where do you make most of your purchases?			Total
		Online	Offline/Retail Stores	A Mix of Both	
Age	10-18	0	0	1	1
	19-26	7	29	19	55
	27-34	1	6	2	9
	34 and Above	0	1	0	1
Total		8	36	22	66

Source: SPSS software

Table 4. Chi-Square Tests

	Value	df	Asymp. Sig. (2-sided)
Pearson Chi-Square	3.491 ^a	6	.745
Likelihood Ratio	4.096	6	.664
Linear-by-Linear Association	.867	1	.352
N of Valid Cases	66		

Source: SPSS software

- a. 9 cells (75.0%) have expected count less than 5. The minimum expected count is .12.

Interpretation: As the p value is more than 0.05, hence we reject H1. This shows that there is no significant association between the age of respondents and where they make most of their purchases.

H3: There is a significant association between the age of respondents and customers' preference for online shopping of electronic items.

Table 4. Crosstab: Age & Customers' Preference for Online Shopping of Electronic Items

		I prefer online shopping for electronic items due to a wider product selection.					Total
		Strongly disagree	Disagree	Neutral	Agree	Strongly agree	
Age	10-18	0	0	0	1	0	1
	19-26	5	10	21	16	3	55
	27-34	2	2	4	1	0	9
	34 and Above	0	0	1	0	0	1
Total		7	12	26	18	3	66

Source: SPSS software

Table 5. Chi-Square Tests

	Value	df	Asymp. Sig. (2-sided)
Pearson Chi-Square	7.067 ^a	12	.853
Likelihood Ratio	7.697	12	.808
Linear-by-Linear Association	2.416	1	.120
N of Valid Cases	66		

Source: SPSS software

- a. 16 cells (80.0%) have an expected count of less than 5. The minimum expected count is .05.

Interpretation: As the p value is more than 0.05, hence we reject H1. This shows that there is no significant association between the age of respondents and customers' preference for online shopping of electronic items.

H4: There is a significant association between the age of respondents and factors influencing customers' choices between online and offline shopping.

Table 6. Crosstab: Age & factor Influencing Customers' Choices between Online and offline shopping

		Convenience is a major factor influencing my choice between online and offline shopping for electronic items.					Total
		Strongly disagree	Disagree	Neutral	Agree	Strongly agree	
Age	10-18	0	0	0	1	0	1
	19-26	4	7	13	25	6	55
	27-34	0	3	5	1	0	9
	34 and Above	0	0	1	0	0	1
Total		4	10	19	27	6	66

Source: SPSS software

Table 7. Chi-Square Tests

	Value	df	Asymp. Sig. (2-sided)
Pearson Chi-Square	12.770a	12	.386
Likelihood Ratio	14.323	12	.281
Linear-by-Linear Association	2.829	1	.093
N of Valid Cases	66		

Source: SPSS Software

- a. 16 cells (80.0%) have an expected count of less than 5. The minimum expected count is .06.

Interpretation: As the p value is more than 0.05, hence we reject H1. This shows that there is no significant association between the age of respondents and factors influencing customers' choices between online and offline shopping.

H5: There is a significant association between the age of respondents and the comparison of Electronic Products online before making a purchase

Table 7. Crosstab: Age & Comparison of Electronic Products Online Before Making a Purchase

		I extensively research and compare electronic products online before making a purchase.					Total
		Strongly disagree	Disagree	Neutral	Agree	Strongly agree	
Age	10-18	0	0	0	0	1	1
	19-26	6	5	4	23	17	55
	27-34	0	2	2	2	3	9
	34 and Above	0	0	1	0	0	1
Total		6	7	7	25	21	66

Source: SPSS Software

Table 8. Chi-Square Tests

	Value	df	Asymp. Sig. (2-sided)
Pearson Chi-Square	15.403a	12	.220
Likelihood Ratio	12.035	12	.443
Linear-by-Linear Association	.531	1	.466
N of Valid Cases	66		

Source: SPSS software

- a. 15 cells (75.0%) have an expected count of less than 5. The minimum expected count is .09.

Interpretation: As the p value is more than 0.05, hence we reject H1. This shows that there is no significant association between the age of respondents and the comparison of Electronic Products online before making a purchase.

DISCUSSION

The demographic data sample shows the core characteristics of the respondents, as age shows smaller participants belong to the age group of 10-18 & 34 and Above which is 1.5% (Vidani, 2015), and the remaining age groups of 19-26 and 27-34 have major proportion of 83.3% and 13.6%. In the data collected gender distribution is fairly balanced with a ratio of males at 51.5% and females at 48.5% (Vidani & Solanki, 2015). The data regarding the educational background of the respondents shows that the majority of participants fall under the category of Master's Degree (59.1%), while 33.3% fall under the category of Bachelor's Degree, and 7.6% fall under the category of High School (Solanki & Vidani, 2016). By the reliability test, we get moderately satisfactory results of 0.714 (Bhatt, Patel, & Vidani, 2017).

According to the analysis, there is no relation ($p = 0.110$) between respondents' age and How Often they shop for electric items such as smartphones, laptops, or gadgets (Niyati & Vidani, 2016). Consequently, H1 is rejected, indicating that customers do not purchase electronic items often (Pradhan, Tshogay, & Vidani, 2016).

According to the analysis, there is no significant relationship ($p = 0.745$) between the age of respondents and where they make most of their purchases (Modi, Harkani, Radadiya, & Vidani, 2016). Hence, H2 is rejected, this shows that customers do not buy electronic items by location (Vidani, 2016).

According to the analysis, there is no connection ($p = 0.853$) between respondents' age and customers' preference for online shopping of electronic items (Sukhanandi, Tank, & Vidani, 2018). Thus, H3 is rejected, which means that customers' preference for shopping online is not affected by the age of the participants (Singh, Vidani, & Nagoria, 2016).

According to the analysis, there is no significant association ($p = 0.386$) between the age of respondents and factors influencing customers' choices between online and offline shopping. Hence, H4 is rejected, which suggests that the customers' choices for online and offline shopping are not influenced by age. According to the analysis, there is a lack of relation ($p = 0.220$) between respondents' age and the comparison of Electronic Products online before making a purchase (Mala, Vidani, & Solanki, 2016). Consequently, H5 is rejected, showing that purchasing electronic products is not influenced by comparative analysis of the products (Dhere, Vidani, & Solanki, 2016).

CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATION

Although the study comprehensively examined the preferences and purchasing habits of Ahmedabad consumers regarding electronic goods, the results are not consistent with any close relationship between the age groups and other components of their purchasing habits. This study makes a valuable contribution by addressing the need for further research in this area, especially in the Ahmedabad region, to gain more information about customer behavior regarding both online and offline shopping.

FURTHER STUDY

Most of the research that has already been done has used quantitative approaches. Further study activities may choose to extend these results with qualitative methods including conversations, interviews or descriptive inquiry. Qualitative approaches provide a more comprehensive understanding by exploring in depth the primary factors, emotions, and motivations that influence customer behavior when it comes to purchasing electronic items. Although the focus of the study was Ahmedabad, similar information can be obtained by expanding the geographical scope to include other Indian cities or regions. Different geographical areas may have particular socio-cultural, economic, or infrastructure factors that influence the way people buy. Examining these differences can provide a more comprehensive understanding of customer preferences in different geographic regions. With long-term persistence, changing patterns and changes in customer behavior may appear. A prospective approach for businesses and governments can be obtained by tracking changes over time between technological improvements, market dynamics and social changes. This will provide useful information about how preferences and behavior change.

REFERENCES

- Bellenger, D.N., Robertson, D.H., & Hirschman, E.C. (1978). Impulse buying varies by product. *Journal of Advertising Research*, 18, 15-18.
- Abdalslam S. I. Mhd.et. al, Impact of trust & past experience on intention to purchase in E-commerce *International journal of Engineering Research & Development* vol 7 iss 10 pp 28-35 Malaysia 2013.
- Williamson O.E (1979) transaction cost economics the governance of contractual relations *journal of law and economics*.

- Bhatt, V., Patel, S., & Vidani, J. N. (2017, February). START-UP INDIA: A ROUGH DIAMOND TO BE POLISHED. National Conference on Startup India: Boosting Entrepreneurship (pp. 61-67). Pune: D.Y. Patil University Press.
- Biharani, S., & Vidani, J. N. (2018). ENTREPRENEURSHIP: CAREER OPPORTUNITY HAS NO GENDER DISCRIMINATION. Compendium of Research Papers of National Conference 2018 on Leadership, Governance and Strategic Management: Key to Success (pp. 101-104). Pune: D. Y Patil University Press.
- Dhere, S., Vidani, J. N., & Solanki, H. V. (2016, November). A SURVEY ON THE TOWARDS SATISFATION LEVEL OF THE CUSTOMER SHOPPING MALL'S: AN ANALYTICAL STUDY. International Multidisciplinary Journal Think Different, 3(24), 45-50.
- Mala, Vidani, J. N., & Solanki, H. V. (2016, November). GREEN MARKETING-A NEW WAY OF MARKETING: A REVIEW APPROACH. International Multidisciplinary Journal Think Different, 3(24), 40-44.
- Modi, R., Harkani, N., Radadiya, G., & Vidani, J. N. (2016, August). Startup India: Even Diamonds start as Coal. NTERNATIONAL JOURNAL FOR INNOVATIVE RESEARCH IN MULTIDISCIPLINARY FIELD, 2(8), 111-116.
- Niyati, B., & Vidani, J. N. (2016, July). Next Generation Children: Smarter or Faster. NTERNATIONAL JOURNAL FOR INNOVATIVE RESEARCH IN MULTIDISCIPLINARY FIELD, 2(7), 110-114.
- Odedra, K., Rabadiya, B., & Vidani, J. (2018). AN ANALYSIS OF IDENTIFYING THE BUSINESS OPPORTUNITY IN AGRO and CHEMICAL SECTOR - WITH SPECIAL REFERENCE TO AFRICAN COUNTRY UGANDA. Compendium of Research Papers of National Conference 2018 on Leadership, Governance and Strategic Management: Key to Success (pp. 96-100). Pune: D.Y Patil University Press.
- Pathak, K. N., & Vidani, J. N. (2016). A SURVEY ON THE AWARENESS SATISFACTION AS WELL ASTO KNOW THE LEVELoF OF THE ONLINE SHOPPING AMONG THE PEOPLE OF AHMADABAD CITY. Governance in E-commerce: Contemporary Issues & Challenges (pp. 261-275). Ahmedabad: GTU.
- Pradhan, U., Tshogay, C., & Vidani, J. N. (2016, July). Short Messages: Its Effect on Teenager's Literacy and Communication. NTERNATIONAL JOURNAL FOR INNOVATIVE RESEARCH IN MULTIDISCIPLINARY FIELD, 2(7), 115-120.
- Rathod, H. S., Meghrajani, D. I., & Vidani, J. (2022, December). Influencer Marketing: A New Marketing Communication Trend. Shodhsamhita, VIII(12(II)), 155-167.
- Sachaniya, C., Vora, H., & Vidani, J. (2019). A Study on Identifying the Gap between Expected service and Actual Service with Special Reference to Suk Sagar Gir Resort, Sasan. In P. Rijwani, S. Shome, & D. Danak (Ed.), BUSINESS, ECONOMY AND ENVIRONMENT: CORPORATE

- PERSPECTIVES (pp. 162-169). Ahmedabad: Himalaya Publishing House Pvt. Ltd.
- Saxena, M., & Vidani, J. N. (2023). MBA Chai Wala. In M. R. Dixit, S. Bist, & S. Shah, *Searching Alternativies* (pp. 22-32). Ahmedabad: Routledge - imprint of Taylor & Francis group.
- Singh, P. K., & Vidani, J. N. (2016, November). PROBLEMS AND PROSPECTS OF AGRICULTURE MARKETING IN INDIA. *International Multidisciplinary Journal Think Different*, 3(22), 9-16.
- Singh, P. K., Vidani, J. N., & Nagoria, V. S. (2016, July-September). Waste Management: Inspire Today for A Better Tomorrow. *Journal of Basic and Applied Engineering Research*, 3(10), 921-926.
- Solanki, H. V., & Vidani, J. N. (2016, November). A NEW ERA OF E-VYAPAR IN 21ST CENTURY: A REVIEW APPROACH. *INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF MULTIDISCIPLINARY EDUCATIONAL RESEARCH*, 5(11(2)), 61-77.
- Solanki, N., & Vidani, J. N. (2016, January). THE STUDY LEGAL ASPECTS OF TRADE IN ETHIOPIA. *ZENITH International Journal of Multidisciplinary Research*, 6(1), 226-284.
- Sukhanandi, S., Tank, D., & Vidani, J. N. (2018). ANALYSIS OF THE IMPACT OF WORK LIFE BALANCE ON WORKING WOMEN LEADER IN INDIA. *National Conference 2018 on Leadership, Governance and Strategic Management: Key to Success* (pp. 77-80). Pune: D.Y.Patil University Press.
- Vasveliya, M., & Vidani, J. (2019). A Study on Analyzing Gap between Expected and Actual Customer Satisfaction Regarding Royal Enfield's Features and Services. In P. Rijwani, S. Shome, & D. Danak (Ed.), *BUSINESS, ECONOMY AND ENVIRONMENT: CORPORATE PERSPECTIVES* (pp. 79-85). Ahmedabad: Himalaya Publishing House Pvt. Ltd.
- Vidani, J. N. (2015, December). "THE STUDY OF THE CONCEPTS OF PERSONALITY TRAITS, VALUES, SKILLS AND PERCEPTION OF DR.MANMOHANSINGH. *The Indian Writer' s e - Journal*, 1(1), 1-14.
- Vidani, J. N. (2015, Novemmmber). Self Aid Group - A Preeminent way for Bucolic Female Empowerment. *International Journal of Advance Engineering and Research Development*, 2(11), 351-360.
- Vidani, J. N. (2015, December). THE STUDY OF INVESTMENT PATTERN OF THE PEOPLE OF BHAVNAGAR DISTRICT. *The Indian Writer's e - Journal*, 1(1), 1-26.
- Vidani, J. N. (2015, December). THE STUDY OF PESTLE ANALYSIS IN KERALA STATE. *ZENITH International Journal of Multidisciplinary Research*, 5(12), 33-50.
- Vidani, J. N. (2016, November). Fake Opportunities and Real Challenges of an Indian Women Entrepreneurs: A Review Approach. *International Journal of Multidisciplinary Educational Research*, 5(11(3)), 224-237.
- Vidani, J. N. (2016). IS ENTREPRENEURSHIP A GENDER BLIND (PART II). *Indian Journal of Technical Education (IJTE) - Special Issue for ICWSTCSC-2016*, 25-33.

- Vidani, J. N. (2016, December). Roles of a Bhartiya Nari Vyapari: A Case study review Approach. *International Journal of Management, IT & Engineering*, 6(12), 328-341.
- Vidani, J. N. (2016, September). Rural Women Entrepreneurship: "Nari Bani Vyapari". *International Journal of Management and Research*, 1, 208-213.
- Vidani, J. N. (2018). *Export and Import Procedures (Vol. 1)*. Online: Educreation Publishing .
- Vidani, J. N. (2018). MERGER AND ACQUISITIONS: A CASE FROM INDIAN TELECOM SECTOR VODAFONE & IDEA. *Compendium of Research Papers of National Conference 2018 on Leadership, Governance and Strategic Management: Key to Success (pp. 105-108)*. Pune: D.Y Patil University Press.
- Vidani, J. N. (2018). Overview of Opportunities and Challenges in Marketing Strategies of Ecopreneurs for their Eco-Pre-natural Products in the Markets of Saurashtra Region. In B. UNNY, D. N. BHATT, & D. S. BHATT (Ed.), *Transformation Through Strategic and Technological Interventions (pp. 159-167)*. Ahmedabad: McGraw Hill Education (India) Private Limited.
- Vidani, J. N. (2019). INFLUENCER MARKETING: A NEW TREND. *National Conference on "Multidisciplinary Research in Social Sciences & Management Studies*. 6, pp. 344-353. Pune: D.Y Patil Institute of Management Studies.
- Vidani, J. N. (2020). ROLE OF WOMEN IN AGRICULTURE SECTOR OF INDIA. In P. (. Mateen, *WOMEN EMPOWERMENT & ECONOMIC DEVELOPMENT (pp. 32-47)*. Kanpur: International Publications.
- Vidani, J. N. (2022). *Digital Marketing for Business in #hashtag era (Vol. 1)*. Delhi, India: Publishing Expert.
- Vidani, J. N., & Das, D. S. (2021, August). A Review on Evolution of Social Media Influencer Marketing: Reflection on Consumer Behaviour and Consumer's Decision-Making Process. *Turkish Online Journal of Qualitative Inquiry (TOJQI)*. Retrieved from <https://www.tojqi.net/index.php/journal/issue/view/51>
- Vidani, J. N., & Dholakia, A. (2020). An Introspective Study on Retail Sector The Current Scenario in Gujarat and India. In R. B. Chauhan, *Management and Innovation: Research Study (pp. 1-15)*. Kanyakumari: Cape Comorin Publisher.
- Vidani, J. N., & Pathak, K. N. (2016). A SURVEY ON AWARENESS AND SATISFACTION LEVEL OF THE CONSUMERS OF ONLINE GIFTING WITH SPECIAL REFERENCE TO AHMADABAD CITY. *Governance in E-commerce: Contemporary Issues & Challenges (pp. 121-135)*. Ahmedabad: GTU.
- Vidani, J. N., & Plaha, N. G. (2016, November). SWACHH BHARAT: CSR INITIATIVE BY INDIAN CORPORATES. *International Multidisciplinary Journal Think Different*, 3(22), 44-50.
- Vidani, J. N., & Plaha, N. G. (2017). AGRIPRENEURSHIP: A REINCARNATION OF INDIAN AGRICULTURAL SECTOR. *Proceedings of the International*

- Conference on Enhancing Economic Productivity and Competitiveness through Financial and Monetary Reforms (pp. 154-159). Ahmedabad: GTU.
- Vidani, J. N., & Singh, P. K. (2017). To study the effect of marketing on awareness and the use of contraceptive pills in the rural areas with special Reference to Ahmedabad District. *Services in Emerging Markets* (pp. 254-265). Ahmedabad: Emerald.
- Vidani, J. N., & Solanki, N. (2015, December). THE STUDY OF FUNDAMENTAL CONCEPTS OF MANAGEMENT FOCUSING ON POSDCORB ANALYSIS - PARLE INDIA PVT. LTD. EXCEL *International Journal of Multidisciplinary Management Studies*, 5(12), 45-56.
- Vidani, J. N., Chack, P. K., & Rathod, D. N. (2017, February). STARTUP INDIA: A CHALLENGING WAY OF THRONES. National Conference on startup India: Boosting Entrepreneurship (pp. 111-118). Pune: D. Y. Patil University Press.